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Supervisor Leadership and Work Climate Outcomes in Calamba City, Laguna NGOs: Training Development Program

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between the managerial skills of administrators and the satisfaction levels of stakeholders in selected government offices in Lipa City. The administrators' profiles revealed that the majority (42.86%) were aged 36-40, predominantly male (71.43%), and mostly married (85.71%). Many had been in their positions for 6-10 years (42.86%) and held a master's degree (64.29%). The assessment of managerial skills indicated that both administrators and subordinates perceived high competence in areas such as approachability and interest in group accomplishments. However, there were noted areas for improvement, such as defining staff duties and using standard criteria for performance assessment. Regarding physical facilities, both groups agreed that administrators ensured conducive environments for education but identified slower response times to requests for improvements. In client relational expertise, administrators and subordinates highlighted inclusive practices but noted lower effectiveness in handling client records and attending meetings. Correlation analysis showed no significant relationships between the administrators' profile variables and their managerial skills, with Pearson r values of 0.62 for human resources management, 0.62 for physical facilities, and 0.67 for client relations. Subordinates expressed high satisfaction with administrators' concern for client safety and growth (mean=3.85), but lower satisfaction with technological and facility improvements (mean=3.31). Clients were generally satisfied with the administrators' provision of quality education (mean=3.79). The study found a highly significant relationship between subordinates satisfaction and administrators' managerial skills, with R^2 values of 0.507 for manpower resources, 0.492 for physical facilities, and 0.551 for client relations, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Conversely, no significant relationship was found between client satisfaction and managerial skills ($R^2=0.007-0.019$), failing to reject the null hypothesis.

Keywords: *behavioral, civil service commission, conceptual, leadership, management*

Introduction

The dynamic landscape of public administration necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing stakeholder satisfaction within government offices. This imperative arises from the increasing complexity and interconnectedness of administrative functions and the growing expectations of stakeholders for transparency, efficiency, and responsiveness in public service delivery. Stakeholders, encompassing employees, clients, and the general public, are vital to the success and legitimacy of government institutions. Therefore, assessing the factors that contribute to their satisfaction is crucial for enhancing the performance and credibility of public administration.

Globally, the significance of effective managerial skills in public administration has been widely recognized. In various countries, studies have underscored the pivotal role of administrators in driving organizational success and enhancing stakeholder satisfaction. Effective managerial practices are seen as key to improving public service delivery and fostering trust between government institutions and the populace. For instance, in countries like the United States and the United Kingdom, public administration reforms have focused on professionalizing the civil service and enhancing managerial competencies through training and development programs. These reforms are aimed at equipping administrators with the skills necessary to navigate the complexities of modern governance, including strategic planning, resource management, and stakeholder engagement.

In the context of developing countries, the emphasis on managerial skills is equally significant. Research conducted in various African and Asian countries has highlighted the correlation between effective management and improved public service outcomes. In these regions, capacity-building initiatives often prioritize the development of leadership and managerial competencies among public administrators. This approach not only enhances the efficiency of government operations but also builds public trust and confidence in government institutions. The global consensus underscores that effective managerial skills are indispensable for achieving high levels of stakeholder satisfaction in public administration.

On a national level, the Philippine government has continuously strived to enhance public service quality through various reforms and initiatives. The performance of government offices has been under scrutiny, with emphasis placed on the managerial competencies of administrators as a critical determinant of organizational efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction. National policies and training programs have been developed to equip government administrators with the necessary skills to meet the demands of their roles and improve the overall quality of public administration.

The Civil Service Commission (CSC) of the Philippines has been instrumental in implementing reforms aimed at professionalizing the bureaucracy and enhancing the managerial capabilities of public administrators. The CSC's programs focus on leadership development,

ethical governance, and strategic management, recognizing that competent and effective managers are essential for delivering high-quality public services. Additionally, the Philippine government's adoption of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RBPMS) underscores the importance of managerial skills in achieving organizational goals and enhancing stakeholder satisfaction. By linking performance outcomes with managerial competencies, the RBPMS fosters a culture of accountability and continuous improvement within the public sector.

Locally, in Calamba City, Laguna, the relationship between administrators' managerial skills and stakeholder satisfaction had not been extensively studied. The unique socio-economic and cultural context of this region presents specific challenges and opportunities for public administration. Local government offices in Calamba City are at the forefront of delivering essential services to the community, and the effectiveness of these services is closely tied to the competencies of their administrators. Understanding how local administrators' managerial skills impact stakeholder satisfaction can provide valuable insights for improving public service delivery at the grassroots level.

Calamba City, a province located in the Region IV A Calabarzon, is characterized by a diverse population and a predominantly agricultural economy. The socio-economic conditions of the province necessitate a responsive and efficient public administration that can address the needs and concerns of its stakeholders. Local government administrators play a crucial role in this context, as they are responsible for implementing policies and programs that directly impact the lives of the community members. Effective managerial skills, including communication, problem-solving, and decision-making, are essential for these administrators to navigate the complexities of local governance and deliver services that meet stakeholder expectations.

By elucidating the relationship between administrators' managerial skills and stakeholder satisfaction, the study aimed to inform policy development, training programs, and managerial practices that could enhance the effectiveness of government offices and better serve the needs of the public. The insights gained from this research could guide local government officials in Calamba City in refining their management approaches to foster a more satisfied and engaged stakeholder base. The identification of key managerial competencies that drive stakeholder satisfaction can inform global and national efforts to professionalize public administration and improve public service delivery.

One significant problem the study encountered was limited access to comprehensive and reliable data. Government offices, particularly at the local level, did not have robust systems in place for collecting and maintaining detailed records of managerial performance and stakeholder satisfaction. Additionally, bureaucratic hurdles and privacy concerns restricted access to pertinent information. Without sufficient data, the study faced challenges in accurately assessing the relationship between administrators' managerial skills and stakeholder satisfaction. The lack of reliable data led to incomplete or biased findings, which did not accurately reflect the true dynamics within the government offices of Calamba City. To mitigate this issue, the study employed alternative data collection methods, such as surveys and interviews, which were time-consuming and did not always yield comprehensive results.

Another potential problem was stakeholder response bias. When collecting data through surveys and interviews, stakeholders did not always provide honest or accurate responses. Various factors contributed to response bias, including fear of reprisal, social desirability, and lack of engagement. For instance, employees hesitated to critique their superiors' managerial skills due to fear of negative consequences, while clients and the general public provided overly positive or negative feedback based on recent experiences or preconceived notions. This response bias skewed the results of the study, leading to an inaccurate assessment of the relationship between managerial skills and stakeholder satisfaction. To address this challenge, the study implemented measures to ensure anonymity and confidentiality for respondents, thereby encouraging more honest and candid feedback. Additionally, using a mixed-methods approach that triangulated data from multiple sources helped to cross-verify the information and reduce the impact of response bias.

Effective managerial skills have been widely recognized as crucial for enhancing public service delivery and fostering trust between government institutions and stakeholders. This study, focusing on the relationship between administrators' managerial skills and stakeholder satisfaction in Calamba City, aimed to provide valuable insights that can inform policy development and managerial practices at the local, national, and global levels. By adopting a holistic approach that considers global trends, national policies, and local contexts, the research sought to contribute to the ongoing efforts to improve public administration and better serve the needs of the public.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the managerial skills of administrators in selected Government offices as a basis for the plan of action. This piece of research purported to answer the following questions.

1. What are the demographic characteristics of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. length of stay in the position; and
 - 1.5. highest educational qualification?
2. How are the managerial skills of the administrators manifested in the management of the curriculum as assessed by

respondents with respect to:

- 2.1. manpower resources;
- 2.2. physical facilities; and
- 2.3. clients relational expertise?
3. Is there a significant correlation between the managerial skills of the administrators and their demographic profile?
4. What are the levels of satisfaction of subordinates and clients relative to managerial skills of the administrators?
5. How do the managerial skills of the administrators relate to the satisfaction of subordinates and that of the clients?
6. Based on the analysis of the results of the study, what plan of action may be recommended for the enhancement of the administrators' managerial skills?

Methodology

Research Design

The study made use of the descriptive research method as it aimed to describe the managerial skills of administrators in Selected Government office. According to Garcia (2020), descriptive research endeavors to describe systematically, factually, accurately and objectively a situation, problem or phenomenon.

The survey questionnaire was used to gather empirical data in assessing the managerial skills of the college administrators in relation to manpower resources, physical facilities, clients' relational expertise and community relational expertise. The survey method likewise determined the level of satisfaction of the subordinates and clients in the exercise of the managerial skills of their administrators. Documentary analysis was also used in the study to substantiate the data about what the researcher wanted to find out regarding the study.

Respondents

The study was conducted in selected government offices in Calamba City, Laguna. The selected offices were Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (PDRRMO) Calamba City, Philippine Red Cross Calamba City and Calamba City Provincial Health Office. There was no sampling method used for the administrators and subordinates because the study maximized the total population and were utilized as respondents. However, the client participants were chosen through a proportionate distribution method. This method is the best-known method in drawing out a random sample. In this method, each member of the population has an equal probability of being selected as a sample. The study determined the desired sample size of 105 clients in ratio and proportion using the Raosoft's formula with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire was developed, validated, administered and scored according to generally accepted practices on research instrumentation. This served as the main data gathering tool.

Part I of the questionnaire covered the demographic characteristics of the administrators and subordinates. Part II dealt with the managerial skills manifested by the administrators of the school as assessed by the three groups of research – participants with respect to manpower resources, physical facilities, and clients relational expertise, while Part III manifested the level of satisfaction of subordinates and clients in the school in the exercise of the managerial skills of the administrators.

The items of the questionnaire were constructed based on readings and concepts of different research that were related to the present study. The first draft was shown to the adviser who went through each item to see if the questions were constructed based on the statement of the problems. Suggestions, corrections and modifications were noted in revising the draft. The second draft was constructed.

To ensure that the questionnaire was correctly and clearly phrased, the researcher requested a language teacher to go over the items. Ambiguous statements were revised to facilitate the giving of answers. After going through the refinement of items, the second draft was presented to the adviser for final checking. Finally, upon the approval of the content structure of the questionnaire, the researcher was then advised to prepare copies for validation.

To validate the questionnaire, the researcher presented the instrument to some knowledgeable persons whose expertise on research matters cannot be questioned. The questionnaire was presented to graduate school professors of Lipa City Colleges Graduate School. The researcher made sure that the questionnaire was properly scrutinized by these experts. Their suggestions and opinions greatly helped to establish the content validity of the instrument. The instrument was validated, and copies were reproduced for distribution.

The researcher personally distributed the questionnaire to intended respondents. To determine the clarity and comprehensiveness of the quality of the questionnaire, a try-out was made to the individuals who were not included in the research.

Procedure

The researcher wrote a letter of request to the administrator of the school asking permission to conduct this study in the institution. As

soon as the permission was granted, letters were sent to the respective administrators and the principal. The researcher made some arrangements as to whether the questionnaire would be personally distributed by the researcher or entrusted to the principal for the administration and retrieval of the accomplished questionnaire.

Given the consent by the principal, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to target respondents. The respondents answered the survey questions for several hours, and then later these were retrieved. The responses of the research participants were tallied, scored and tabulated for statistical treatment.

Data Analysis

The following statistics were used in the study

Frequency Percentage and Rank. These were used to describe distribution of the participants of the study based on demographic profile.

Weighted mean. This was used to analyze the extent of satisfaction of the clients on the managerial skills of administrators.

t-test. This was used to find out the significant differences between the responses of the clients and the subordinates on the administrators' managerial skills.

Chi-square test. This was used to determine the relationship between managerial skills and the satisfaction of the subordinates and clients.

Scheffe Test. This was used to test the significant difference in the level of satisfaction of the subordinates and clients on the exercise of the managerial skills of the administrators.

Raosoft's formula. This was used to determine the sample size of the clients' participants.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical considerations for this study were paramount in ensuring integrity, transparency, and respect for all participants involved. First and foremost, informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. This process involved providing clear and comprehensive information about the study's objectives, methods, potential risks, and benefits. Participants were made aware that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. This ensured that all participants were fully informed and voluntarily agreed to take part in the research.

Confidentiality and anonymity were critical components of the ethical framework. The study ensured that all data collected from participants were kept strictly confidential. Personal identifiers were removed, and data were anonymize to protect the identities of the participants. This was particularly important in reducing response bias and encouraging honest and candid feedback, especially among employees who might fear reprisal for criticizing their superiors. Additionally, data were securely stored and only accessible to the research team to prevent unauthorized access or breaches of confidentiality.

Another key ethical consideration was the potential impact of the study's findings on the participants and the organizations involved. The study carefully considered how the results would be reported to avoid any negative repercussions for individual participants or government offices. Findings were presented in aggregate form, without singling out specific individuals or offices, to ensure that the results could be used constructively for improving managerial practices and stakeholder satisfaction without causing harm.

The study also adhered to ethical guidelines for conducting research with human subjects, as outlined by relevant ethical review boards. This included obtaining ethical clearance and ensuring that the research design, data collection methods, and analysis adhered to high ethical standards. The study was committed to minimizing any potential harm or discomfort to participants, and mechanisms were in place to address any concerns or issues that arose during the research process.

Finally, the study-maintained transparency throughout its duration. Participants were regularly updated on the progress of the research and were provided with access to the results. This fostered a sense of trust and collaboration between the researchers and participants, ensuring that the study was conducted with the utmost respect for the rights and dignity of all involved. By adhering to these ethical considerations, the study aimed to contribute valuable insights to the field of public administration while upholding the highest standards of ethical research practice.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study gives the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Profile of the Administrators

Distribution of the administrators as to age.

Table 1 shows the age distribution of the administrators from the participating school. The study investigated the demographic profile of the administrators with respect to age, highest educational attainment, sex, gender, civil status, length of time, the position and length

of stay in the institution. Data on the table show that six or 42.86 percent of the administrators were on the age bracket of 36 – 40; three or 21.43 percent were on age bracket of 31 – 35; two or 14.29 percent were on the 51 and above age bracket and one or 7.14 percent each was on age brackets of 25 – 30, 41 – 45 and 46 – 50 years old. It can be gleaned from the data that the greatest number of respondents was in the age bracket of 36 to 40 which ranked first in the rank order distribution and the least was those who were on age brackets of 25 – 30, 41 – 45 and 46 – 50 years old.

Table 1. *Age Distribution of Administrators*

<i>Age Bracket</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
25-30	1	7.14	5
31-35	3	21.43	2
36-40	6	42.86	1
41-45	1	7.14	5
46-50	1	7.14	5
51 and above	2	14.29	3
Total	14	100	

It can be deduced from the data that the administrators in the Selected Government office are on their adult age. Age determines the decision skills of a person. In this case the administrators of the school are as manifested in their age, more capable of administering their managerial skills and matured enough to know the factors that would satisfy the subordinates and clients. It can be gleaned that based on the mean age; it can be concluded that the administrators in general can handle their administrative position.

The result of the present study affirmed the work of Flores whose study about the managerial and supervisory practices of empowered public school heads emphasized the relationship of the profile of the administrators with their managerial and supervisory practices. She found out that age had significant relationship with their management performance.

Distribution of administrators as to sex.

Table 2. *Distribution of Administrators in Terms of Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Male	4	28.57	2
Female	10	71.43	1
Total	14	100	

Table 2 presents the distribution of the administrators according to sex. Data on the table show that most or ten or 71.43 percent of the administrators were female and four or 28.57 percent were male coordinators. As manifested from the data, the female coordinators dominated the male in the school under study. This proved that education is still a female-dominated profession. However, data also showed that there were male coordinators in the field inferring that slowly sex is not a prediction to administrative management in the school.

The study of Flores about managerial and supervisory practices of empowered public elementary and school heads presented strong evidence that the profile of the administrators was related to the managerial skills of the administrators. She further found out that female and male administrators did not differ on how they performed their managerial skills when applied to management of human resources and physical facilities.

Distribution of administrators as to civil status.

Table 3. *Civil Status of the Administrators*

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Single	2	14.29	2
Married	12	85.71	1
Total	14	100	

The demographic characteristics of coordinators according to their civil status are treated in Table 3. Data on the table reveals that majority of the respondents, comprised of 12 or 85.71 percent of the coordinators were married, while two or 14.29 percent were single. It can be gleaned from the data that there were more married coordinators in the school where the study was conducted.

It can be deduced that most of the coordinators were married as they are mostly in their late 30's and therefore likely to have partners in life. This result sustains the self-actualization concept postulated by Apruebo (2019) which posited that part of the basic needs of individuals is to have his accomplishments and achievements, which in this study is self-actualization on establishing marital partnership.

Distribution of the administrators as to length of stay in the position.

Table 4 describes the coordinators' demographic distribution according to their length of stay in the school. Data on the table show that six or 42.86 percent of the administrators had been in their institution for six to 10 years; three or 21.43 percent were with their

institution for 16 - 20 years and two or 14.29 percent each had been in their institution for 11 – 15 and 20 years and above, respectively. Only one or 7.14 percent had stayed in the position for less than five years.

Table 4. *Length of Stay in the Position*

<i>Length of stay in the position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Below 5 years	1	7.14	5
6-10 years	6	42.86	1
11-15 years	2	14.29	3.5
16-20 years	3	21.43	2
21-and above	2	14.29	3.5
Composite Mean = 6			
Total	14	100	

It can be gleaned from the data that the greatest number of administrators had been working in the school for six to ten years and the least number with at least below five years. This tends to imply that they could have developed capability to perform their tasks as coordinators, as they already know how the system works in their institution. It this is in the thinking that experienced workers such as the respondents are more skillful than the less experienced in performing their assigned tasks. With their professional preparation, they have the capability and good knowledge in their present jobs. They have the technical know-how; know the do's and don'ts for the upliftment and success of their institution. The workers stay in their position for a long time; they are expected to impart or share their experiences to others such as creating strategic plans and working for their implementation.

Distribution of administrators as to highest educational attainment.

Table 5. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Administrators*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Baccalaureate Degree	1	7.14	4
Master's Degree	9	64.29	1
Doctoral Degree	2	14.29	2.5
No answer	2	14.29	2.5
Total	14	100	

The demographic profile of respondents as regard to highest educational attainment is covered in Table 5. Data on the Table 5 show that nine or 64.29 percent of the administrators were master's degree holders which ranked first in the rank order. Two or 14.29 percent were doctoral degree holders and only one or 7.14 percent was a baccalaureate degree holder.

Data showed that generally, most of them were masters' degree holders. This infers that they met the requirements on educational attainment. The master's degree is a formal and professional assurance that the administrators is educationally prepared to lead and manage subordinates and implement the curriculum.

The results of the study on the educational qualification of administrators find similarity to the study of Aseron which was about the managerial skills of administrators of the District of San Luis. In the study, educational proficiency includes solid foundation in liberal studies, which implies that administrators must have thorough understanding of bodies of knowledge broader than their specialty. Other fields of studies enhanced administrator's know-how. In this study, having a master's degree was the quality assurance on the preparedness of heads in their administrative positions.

Assessment on the Managerial Skills of the Administrators

Managerial skills in management of manpower resources

The assessment of administrators and subordinates on the coordinators' managerial skills regarding the management of manpower resources are shown in Table 6. The managerial capabilities of the coordinators about manpower, physical facilities, client relational expertise and community relational expertise were assessed by the two groups of respondents. Data on their assessments are shown in the preceding tables.

Results from the table show that both coordinators and subordinates gave their highest assessment of 3.85 and 4.33 on that the administrators were easy to approach and manifested interested in their accomplishments. These are indicative of the affective leadership they showed in school which may motivate better cooperation in school activities.

Both respondents likewise noted that to a greater extent, administrators were open to grievances of family and listen to them, with next higher weighted mean s of 3.75 and 3.65 as cited by coordinators and 4.23 and 4.15 by subordinates. These reflected coordinators' effectiveness in dealing with subordinates thus allowing them to open up to administrators, ranked, 2nd and 3rd among the items.

Fourth in rank among the coordinators was 3.67 on that to a greater extent they used standard criteria for staff performance while showed their objectivity in dealing with the subordinates. However, subordinates gave higher importance that their head gave them subject assignments which were compensated well, indicated in weighted mean of 4.00. On the other hand, lowest among the items was 3.60 on the coordinators' assessment that the defined duties and functions of subordinates and allowed them to be creative; while

lowest among the subordinates was 3.62 on use of standard criteria to rate their performance.

Table 6. *Managerial Skills of the Administrators as Manifested in the Management of Manpower Resources*

Managerial Skills	Administrators			Teacher			Overall		
	WM	VI	Rank	WM	VI	Rank	WM	VI	Rank
The administrators and principal:									
1. give freedom to subordinates to voice out whatever grievance they have,	3.75	GE	2	4.15	GE	3	3.95	GE	3
2. give subject assignments to subordinates with fair compensation,	3.65	GE	5	4.00	GE	4	3.82	GE	4
3. benefits and incentives	3.61	GE	6	3.92	GE	5	3.77	GE	5
4. lay out clear-cut and strategic plans on the policies and programs to be implemented									
5. are friendly and listens not only to subordinates but to all members of the organization									
6. are easy to talk with,									
7. approachable, and show interest to the accomplishments of the group	3.72	GE	1	4.33	GE	1	4.09	GE	1
8. define the functions and duties of the staff and allow them to exercise creativity	3.85	GE	1	4.33	GE	1	4.09	GE	1
9. use standard criteria for assessing staff performance	3.60	GE	7	3.85	GE	6	3.72	GE	6
10. give due recognition to accomplishments and encourage them to grow professionally	3.67	GE	4	3.62	GE	7	3.64	GE	7
Composite Mean	3.69	GE		4.01	GE		3.85	GE	

It can be gleaned from the data that the highest weighted mean for the responses of the administrators and subordinates was given to the attribute of the coordinators of being approachable and interested on the performance of the subordinates. Moreover, it appears that both administrators and subordinates dealt fairly with each other. However, there was a need for administrators to define the functions and duties of the staff and allow them to exercise creativity so that they may become more cooperative and aware of their duties. On the other hand, subordinates wanted a standard criterion to assess staff performance due recognition to their accomplishments. This is important so that as it will make subordinates aware of their performance. Also, subordinates will exercise their work and obligations independently without any direct supervision of their superiors. Composite mean was 3.85 indicating manpower management was performed to a greater extent.

The two groups of respondents, as shown in results of their responses, believed that the administrators’ managerial skills in managing manpower resources were manifested to a greater extent. As Schermerhan stated, administrators must possess human relation expertise. They must have the skills and abilities to interact effectively with people in their organization. Genuine skills in human relations are often revealed by a sense of humor, friendly manner with people, an ability to adapt quickly to the social level of a group, and capability to lead others in action. Along with the same concept, Stoner cited that administrators must possess basic skills such as technical, conceptual and human skills.

In the local setting, Aquino emphasized also that school administrators must possess human skills, which are ways on how to deal with people effectively. Administrators must establish trust and confidence among their subordinates to develop productivity and sense of responsibility. If proper human relations provides the staff they need, the goals of the organization will likely be easy to be attained.

Leadership of administrators as managers involves influencing others to engage in the behavior necessary to reach emotional goals. Successful organizations regard leadership skill requirement as a high priority concern of managers. These are expected to provide the required outputs by utilizing the various inputs including labor.

Managerial skills in management of physical facilities.

The assessment of the two groups of respondents regarding the managerial skills of administrators regarding physical facilities management is shown in Table 7.

Results of assessment on management of physical facilities showed that the highest weighted means of 3.74 and 4.15 were given by two groups of respondents. Both groups noted that the administrators ensured the school buildings were conducive to learning implying that cleanliness was ensured in all the places in the school.

Ranked 2nd by both groups was that coordinators ensured coordination with maintenance department on safety measures which had weighted means of 3.74 and 3.72. This indicated that to a greater extent they made safety a priority.

Administrators likewise cited that to a greater extent administrators scheduled priority program and project and controlled and supervised school equipment, weighted mean of 3.57 but which were given lower assessment by the subordinates, the prioritization of program was not done fairly. Lowest assessment among administrators was 3.35 on that to a greater extent they took immediate action on requests for improvement of school facilities; among the subordinates however, this had higher weighted mean of 3.85 indicating

positive assessment that administrators immediately addressed need for facilities improvement. On the part of the clients lowest weighted mean was on acquisition of modern equipment inferring that they wanted their school to be updated in learning. It can be gleaned from the data that the highest assessment given by the administrators and subordinates was on provision of school environment conducive to quality education such as having offices, utilities and classrooms.

Table 7. *Managerial Skills Manifested in the Management of Physical Facilities*

Managerial Skills	Administrators			Subordinates			Overall		
	WM	VI	Rank	WM	VI	Rank	WM	VI	Rank
The administrators and head make sure that:									
1. school buildings and premises are conducive to quality education by providing and maintaining cleanliness of all offices, utilities and classrooms	3.74	GE	1.5	4.15	GE	1	3.95	GE	1
2. frequent coordination with the maintenance department is being given to ensure safety measures are observed	3.74	GE	1.56	3.92	GE	2	3.83	GE	2
3. provisions and maintenance for modern technology to be abreast with modern trends in education are provided	3.41	GE	3.5	3.38	GE	7	3.40	GE	7
4. control and supervision of school equipment is very evident	3.57	GE	7	3.69	GE	4	3.63	GE	3
5. immediate action is taken regarding requests that affect the improvement/enhancement of school facilities	3.35	GE	5	3.85	GE	3	3.60	GE	4
6. monitoring and checking of equipment and the whole workplace premises are occasionally done	3.44	GE	5	3.54	GE	5.5	3.49	GE	6
7. scheduling of priority programs and projects are done fairly	3.57	GE	3.5	3.54	GE	5.5	3.56	GE	5
Composite Mean	3.54	GE		3.73	GE		3.65		

The least was the assessment of clients on provision and maintenance for modern technology to be abreast with modern trends in education. Data further revealed that composite mean was 3.63 indicating that management of facilities by administrators was to a greater extent.

Based from the results of the responses, both administrators and subordinates showed affirmation on the skill of administrators in managing facilities in school. This shows leadership of administrators in the context of use and care of physical facilities relevant to learning. As cited by Franco, management of resources, both material and human resources showed be well-planned. Resources are wasted when insufficient or not fully utilized which may affect realization of end goals.

Managerial skills with regard to client relational expertise.

Table 8. *Managerial Skills of the Administrators as Manifested in Client Relational Expertise*

Managerial Skills	Administrators			Subordinates			Overall	
	WM	VI	Rank	WM	VI	Rank	WM	VI
The administrators and head:								
1. are friendly, approachable and knows how to be liked by the clients recognize clients' accomplishments,	3.78	GE	4	4.08	GE	2.5	3.93	GE
2. give rewards and provide motivation for them to excel more	3.85	GE	2.5	3.69	GE	5	3.77	GE
3. include clients in school activities so as to develop them holistically monitor daily progress of clients,	3.89	GE	1	4.31	GE	1	4.10	GE
4. know their needs, and study the problems that affect their academic performance	3.59	GE	6	3.69	GE	5	3.64	GE
5. are concerned with clients' safety, values, growth and ideals	3.85	GE	2.5	4.08	GE	2.5	3.96	GE
6. attend to clients' meetings regarding school activities and programs	3.64	GE	5	3.62	GE	7	3.63	GE
7. call the attention of the Guidance Counselor to give a report on record of clients	3.53	GE	7	3.69	GE	5	3.61	GE
Composite Mean	3.73	GE		3.88	GE		3.80	GE

Table 8 presents the assessment of administrators and subordinates on the managerial skills in relation to the administrators' clients' relational expertise.

Of the data of client relation expertise, ranked first by both administrators and subordinates was inclusion of clients in school activities for their holistic development. This had the highest weighted mean of 3.89 on administrators' assessment and 4.31 representing subordinates assessments. This is indicative that for both groups of respondents, the administrators give top priority on the holistic development of clients.

Administrators ranked 2nd with weighted mean of 3.85 that they recognized and gave awards to clients' exemplary performance as motivation for them to do better; this concern however 5th among the subordinates was indicating that this was not as much addressed

by administrators.

Both groups, however, agreed and ranked 2nd that administrators attended clients' meetings which concerns clients' activities and programs with weighted means of 3.85 and 4.08. The results infer that administrators found way to morally support and encourage client participation in school programs and activities.

The subordinates on the other hand also placed in 2nd as indicated in 4.08 weighted mean the characteristics of being friendly and approachable of administrators. This result infers that this trait is highly appreciated by clients and is evident among administrators.

The lowest and last in rank among administrators was 3.53 on that to a greater extent the administrators required the Guidance Counselor to provide report of clients' record. This concern, however, was 5th among subordinates indicating that the administrators actually required Guidance Counselors to report on clients grades.

The lowest weighted mean among the subordinates was 3.62 on attendance of administrators to clients' meeting implying that of all concerns on clients, this was least prioritized by administrators.

The composite mean was 3.85 indicating administrators performed to a greater extent concerns of clients. The two groups of respondents both believed that the administrators' performed their task of developing client relationships. Tendero justified that productive heads are interested in how groups of clients are performing and facilitate clients' learning. In doing so, their actions serve as a model for the actualization of the learning process.

Correlation between the Managerial Skills and the Profile Variables of the Administrators

Relationship between the profile variables and management of manpower resources.

Table 9. Relationship between the Managerial Skills and Profile Variables of Administrators as to Management of Manpower Resources

Profile	Beta Coefficient	t-Value	P-Value	Significance
Age	-0.20	-0.74	0.74	Not Significant
Sex	0.17	0.18	0.87	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.81	0.71	0.51	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.35	-0.38	0.72	Not Significant
Position	0.48	-1.63	0.15	Not Significant
Length of stay in the Position	0.23	-0.37	0.73	Not Significant
Length of stay in the institution	-0.15	-0.28	0.80	Not Significant
Significance of Regression				
Person R	0.60	Not Significant		
R square	0.37			
f-value	0.49			
Probability Value	0.81			
Intercept	6.22			

The study investigated the relationship between managerial skills and the profile variables of administrators. Table 9 determined significant relationship between the profile variables and managerial skills of administrators with respect to manpower resources.

Data on the table show the relationship between the managerial skills and the profile variables of administrators as regard to management of manpower resources. Results from the table reflect that there were no significant relationships between managerial skills of administrators and their profile variables as to management of manpower resources as shown in t-value of 0.74 when considering age, 0.87, as to sex, 0.51, as to civil status, 0.72, as to highest educational attainment and 0.15, as to position. Length of stay in the position had t-value of 0.73, and length of stay in the institution has t-value of 0.80. The results showed that the profile variables of the administrators have no significant values with how the administrators performed their managerial skills as regard to manpower resources.

The relationship between the managerial skills and profile variables of administrators as regard to management of manpower resources tended to show that profile variables had no significant value to how the administrators manages the manpower resources as indicated in Pearson R of 0.60. The computed beta coefficient that was the result of using significance regression model indicated this. Thus, the df as shown by the computed t-value and probability value of which were above the 0.05 level of significance, led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Relationship between profile variables and management of physical facilities.

Data on Table 10 show the relationship between the profile variables and the administrators' managerial skills with respect to management of physical facilities. Data on the table shows the relationship between the managerial skills and the profile variables of the administrators as regard to management of physical facilities. Data reveal there were no significant relationships between managerial skills and profile variables as shown in the t-value of 0.84 for age, 0.57, sex, 1.00, for civil status and 0.78, for education attainment. Position had t-value of 0.11, and t-value of 0.89 and 0.55 for length of stay in the position and the institution. These results

revealed that the administrators' profile variables were not significant values with how the administrators managed physical facilities.

Table 10. *Relationship between the Managerial Skills and Profile Variables of Administrators as Regard to Management of Physical Facilities*

Profile	Beta Coefficient	t-Value	P-Value	Significance
Age	0.11	0.21	0.84	Not Significant
Sex	0.53	-0.60	0.57	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.00	0.00	1.00	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.25	-0.30	0.78	Not Significant
Position	-0.50	-1.86	0.11	Not Significant
Length of stay in the Position	-0.08	-0.14	0.89	Not Significant
Length of stay in the institution	-0.34	-0.63	0.55	Not Significant
Significance of Regression				
Person R	0.60	Not Significant		
R square	0.38			
f-value	0.53			
Probability Value	0.79			
Intercept	7.44			

The regression analysis which resulted to Pearson R of 0.62 indicated that the profile had no significant relationship to how the administrators managed the physical facilities. The computed beta coefficient that was the result of using significance regression model indicated this. Thus, the df as shown by the computed t-values and probability values tended to accept of the null hypothesis.

Relationship between profile variables and client relational expertise of administrators.

Table 11. *Relationship between the Managerial Skills and Profile Variables of Administrators as to Client Relational Expertise*

Profile	Beta Coefficient	t-Value	P-Value	Significance
Age	0.17	0.36	0.73	Not Significant
Sex	0.77	-0.98	0.37	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.15	0.16	1.88	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.10	-0.14	0.89	Not Significant
Position	-0.44	-1.84	0.12	Not Significant
Length of stay in the Position	-0.16	-0.32	0.76	Not Significant
Length of stay in the institution	-0.25	-0.54	0.61	Not Significant
Significance of Regression				
Person R	0.67	Not Significant		
R square	0.45			
f-value	0.69			
Probability Value	0.68			
Intercept	7.49			

The relationship between the managerial skills of administrators in relation to client relational expertise and the profile variables are presented in Table 11.

The relationship between the managerial skills and the profile variables of the administrators as regard to the client relational expertise results from Table 11 show that there were no significant relationships between managerial skills and profile variables of administrators considering client relational expertise as indicated in t-value of 0.73, for age, 0.37, for sex, 0.37, for civil status and 0.98, for highest educational attainment. The variables of position had t-value of 0.12, 0.76, for length of stay in the position and 0.65 for length of stay in the institution.

As gleaned from the table, results from the regression showed Pearson R of 0.67 showing no significant relationship between the managerial skills as regard to client relational expertise and the profile variables of administrators. The computed beta coefficient that was the result of using significance regression model indicated this. The computed t-values and probability values tended to imply the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

This means that the managerial skills of the college administrators of the three engineering colleges about client relational expertise have nothing to do with their profile variables.

Level of Satisfaction of Subordinates and Clients on the Managerial Skills of their Administrators

Level of satisfaction of subordinates in relation to managerial skills of administrators.

Data on Table 12 present the level of satisfaction of the subordinates on the managerial skills as manifested in the management of manpower resources, management of physical facilities, client relational expertise and community relational expertise.

Table 12. *Level of Satisfaction of the Subordinates towards the Managerial Skills of the Administrators*

<i>Managerial Skills</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
Assignments of teaching load, salary and other benefits	3.66	Much Satisfied
Academic freedom in the workplace	3.83	Much Satisfied
Implementation of strategic plans and programs	3.57	Much Satisfied
Supervisory practices in the workplace	3.59	Much Satisfied
Creativity in performance of duty	3.75	Much Satisfied
Assessment of staff and subordinates performance	3.57	Much Satisfied
Conduciveness and management of school buildings and premises	3.57	Much Satisfied
Observance of safety measures	3.50	Much Satisfied
Acquisition and maintenance of modern technology and improvement/enhancement of school facilities	3.31	Much Satisfied
Control and supervision of school equipment, tools and machinery	3.50	Much Satisfied
Concern to clients' safety, values, growth and ideals	3.85	Much Satisfied
Monitoring of clients' development by studying factors affecting academic performance	3.65	Much Satisfied
Exploration on the educational needs and problems of the community	3.65	Much Satisfied
Provision of civic activities needed for the betterment of the community and clientry	3.65	Much Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.62	Much Satisfied

The data show that out of 13 variables enumerated there was one variable, which had verbal interpretation of satisfied. This was on acquisition and maintenance of modern technology and improvement/enhancement of school facilities with a weighted mean of 3.31. The rest of the variables were described as much satisfied.

It could be treated that subordinates were much satisfied on the administrators' concern on clients' safety, academic freedom in the workplace and creativity in the performance of duty. These were given high assessments among all the items indicating that the subordinates placed great importance to these skills of administrators.

Likewise, there was much satisfaction among the subordinates on their teaching loads as well as their salary and benefits, mean of 3.66. Moreover, there was much satisfaction on the administrators' effort to study factors affecting academic performance, finding educational needs of community and provision of civic activities for the community which had some mean of 3.65. Subordinates likewise manifested much satisfaction on the administrators' implementation of strategic plans, staff and subordinates assessment and management school of school building.

It can be gleaned from the data that the highest assessment was on administrators' concern to clients' safety, values, growth and ideals wherein subordinates expressed much satisfaction. It can be deduced from the data that the administrators give highest priority for the clients. However, they clear that there is much room for improvement needed in the acquisition and maintenance of modern technology and improvement/enhancement of school facilities.

Tendero in his study about job satisfaction of subordinates in selected schools cited that to satisfy the subordinates, the administrators must make the subordinates see the need to be aware of the direct and indirect effects of the physical environment to achieve the competence and instructional goals. They must help the subordinates and clients get the right values into their hearts, the right skills in their hands and put the right ideas into their minds.

Level of satisfaction of clients in relation to management skills of administrators.

Table 13. *Level of Satisfaction of the Clients in relation to Management Skills of Administrators*

<i>Managerial Skills</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
Quality education provided	3.79	Much Satisfied
Provision for amenities such as laboratory, canteen, reading centers, library and others	3.14	Satisfied
Quality service from the office personnel	3.32	Satisfied
Qualifications of Subordinates	3.70	Much Satisfied
Academic freedom and freedom to express one's self	3.30	Satisfied
Security and safety inside the workplace	3.44	Satisfied
Sense of importance in the institution	3.28	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.42	Satisfied

Data on Table 13 present satisfaction of the clients in the three tertiary schools on the managerial skills of administrators and heads. Results from the table show that clients were very satisfied with the quality education provided, with mean of 3.79 and on qualifications of subordinates, with weighted mean of 3.70.

These affirmed clients were appreciative of the education they receive from their school and the qualifications of subordinates reflected in their teaching. Clients were also satisfied with security and safety inside the workplace, service of the office personnel, academic freedom and freedom to express oneself which had weighted means of 3.30 – 3.32. The clients were also satisfied with the importance in the institution and provision of amenities as lavatory, canteen, reading centers, library and others with weighted means of 3.28 and 3.14.

The data revealed that the clients were very satisfied with the qualifications of subordinates. However, they are only satisfied with their other expectations from their administrators and heads. The results of the study affirm the concepts of Dalain and Aquino. Dalain in her study found out that a healthy workplace and satisfaction of individual needs motivate people and satisfaction of individual needs motivate people and help attain the goals of the organization.

Taken from Aquino's concept, school administrators tasks do not only include instruction and curriculum development, staff resources, community relations, school plant and facilities but also include clients' resources and inventory and must have continued concern for the clients learning and provision of good learning environment.

Relationship between the Managerial Skills of the School Administrators and the Level of Satisfaction of the Subordinates and Clients

Table 14. Relationship between the Level of Satisfaction of the Subordinates and Clients and the Managerial Skills of the Administrators

	Pearson r	R-square	P-value	Significance	Decision
Subordinates					
Manpower Resources	0.712	0.507	<0.01	Highly Sig.	Reject Ho
Physical Facilities	0.705	0.497	<0.01	Highly Sig.	Reject Ho
Client Relational Expertise	0.742	0.551	<0.01	Highly Sig.	Reject Ho
Community Relational Expertise	0.768	0.551	<0.01	Highly Sig.	Reject Ho
Clients					
Manpower resources	0.027	0.001	0.845	Not Sig.	Fail Reject Ho
Physical Facilities	0.031	0.0001	0.790	Not Sig.	Fail Reject Ho
Client Relational Expertise	0.137	0.019	0.323	Not Sig.	Fail Reject Ho
Community Relational Expertise	0.135	0.018	0.335	Not Sig.	Fail Reject Ho

Table 14 shows the data about the relationship between the level of satisfaction of the subordinates and clients as regard to the managerial skills of the college administrators as manifested in the management manpower resources, physical facilities, client relational expertise and community relational expertise.

Data show that there was highly significant relationship between level of satisfaction and managerial skills as regard to management of manpower resources, physical facilities, client and community relational expertise as shown by the computed R² values of 0.507, 0.497, 0.551 and 0.551, respectively. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that the satisfaction of the subordinates is highly affected by the managerial skills of the college administration. The results suggest that the managerial skills of the college administrators determine whether the subordinates will appreciate their efforts. How they treat people, address needs for facilities development and their endeavors to win cooperation of clients and community will affect satisfaction of their subordinates.

However, there was no significant relationship between clients' satisfaction and managerial skills of administration as management of manpower resources, Pearson r 0.845, physical facilities, 0.790, client relational expertise, 0.323 and for community relational expertise, 0.335. These findings indicate no significant value to the level of satisfaction of the clients; thus, it fails to reject the null hypothesis.

As gleaned from the data, there is strong evidence that there is a high relationship between the level of satisfaction and managerial skills. This can be proven by them because they are the direct observers and recipients of how the college administrators' managerial skills are implemented in the college.

However, there was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction of the clients and managerial skills of the college administrators. This result cannot be questioned because as a client it is not their concern how the college administrators manage the manpower resources, and physical facilities. Also, it seemed clients were not as interested in the skills of administrators on clients and community relational expertise. Usually, clients are not so interested in these matters. The clients of today go to school and do what the subordinates want them to do but are not much concerned about college affairs unless or once informed. It can be concluded that the clients' level of satisfaction has no strong relationship with the managerial skills of the administrators of the three engineering colleges.

Conclusions

Based on the summary and findings of the study, the researcher reached the following conclusions:

The analysis revealed that the majority of administrators were middle-aged, married males who had been in their positions for no more than five years. This profile indicated that most administrators were relatively new to their roles within the institution, reflecting a phase of transition and adaptation.

Additionally, the study showed that administrators demonstrated considerable proficiency in various managerial skills. These included the management of manpower resources, physical facilities, and relational expertise with both clients and the community. The findings suggested that administrators generally performed well in these areas, as evaluated by both their self-assessment and feedback from

subordinates.

Moreover, the data indicated that the administrators' demographic variables—such as age, sex, civil status, length of tenure, and educational attainment—did not significantly affect their management of manpower resources, physical facilities, or clients' relational expertise. This lack of significant correlation suggested that these personal attributes did not notably influence administrators' performance in these areas.

The study also found a high level of satisfaction among subordinates regarding the administrators' managerial skills. Subordinates were generally pleased with how administrators managed their responsibilities. In contrast, while clients expressed satisfaction with the administrators' skills, their satisfaction levels were less pronounced compared to those of the subordinates. This difference pointed to a disparity in how internal staff and external clients perceived the effectiveness of administrative management.

Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between the administrators' managerial skills and the level of satisfaction reported by subordinates. This relationship indicated that subordinates' satisfaction was strongly influenced by the administrators' competencies. However, this connection did not extend to clients' satisfaction, suggesting that the factors affecting client satisfaction were not as closely linked to the administrators' skills.

Finally, the study concluded that implementing a well-designed plan of action could be beneficial for sustaining and further developing administrators' managerial skills. Such a plan would address identified areas for improvement and support ongoing professional development, emphasizing the importance of continuous learning and adaptation to enhance administrative effectiveness.

The study provided important insights into the profiles of administrators, their managerial skills, and the impact of these factors on stakeholder satisfaction. The findings highlighted the need for targeted interventions and ongoing development to support administrators and improve satisfaction among both subordinates and clients.

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher hereby recommends the following:

The college administrators and heads must have a continuous and maintain evaluation of the output of their school programs to find out where the lapses are to effect the necessary changes and improvements. They may schedule dialogues with the clients and subordinates to discuss matters regarding their school activities and school problems affecting their curricular achievement.

Subordinates must prove to the administration that they follow the code of ethics of teaching in order for administrators to recognize their contribution to the school. Grievances regarding their job may be channeled to the appropriate forum.

Clients must be encouraged to communicate with the administration through proper channels to voice out their grievances they want the administration to do for them.

The proposed action plan for the enhancement/sustainable program for the development of managerial skills may be tried out and refined prior to implementation

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